

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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"HANDS-ON EXPERIENCES: TRANSFORMING THE TVL CLASSROOM INTO AN INDUSTRY-BASED SETUP"

Liliw Senior High School is one of the potential secondary schools in Laguna situated at Barangay Ibabang Taykin, Liliw, Laguna which is 10 minutes away from the sub-office and 60 minutes away from the division office. The school site has a total land area of one thousand five hundred square meters (1,500 sq. m.). The school program offerings are Academic and Technical Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) track specifically in the Home Economics strand focusing on Food and Beverage Services (FBS) NC II. The teachers make sure that most of the students cultivate technical and vocational skills relevant to various industries. To enhance their education and meet the demands of industry, the school decided to transform its existing TVL classroom into an industry-based setup, aligning with the Division of Laguna's Project Industry-Based Laboratory Management (IBLM). The goal of this program to build a good foundation of students' practical skills and theoretical knowledge while working in laboratories having an industrial interface. Project IBLM wants to bridge performance gaps in classrooms on the foundation of skill development comes along with academic performance assessment. Through this project, the school targets to upgrade the standard of education and skill-development available to students, showing to increase learning outcomes and future prospects. Additionally, it allows to familiarize themselves with workplace dynamics, apply their skills in genuine work settings, and engage in employment simulations. During the implementation of the project, one of the difficulties encountered by the school in conducting real-life laboratory practicums for SHS TVL learners is the shortage of adequate resources and facilities. Since this program is a technology-driven project, it often requires specialized equipment, tools, and materials that schools may not have due to budget limitations. This lack of resources can restrict students' ability to attain practical skills and diminish the scope and quality of their projects. In response to these challenges, Schools Division Office of Laguna has generously provided tools, materials, and equipment intended at dwelling the identified needs of learners. With this support, the school ensures that each student's academic journey in Food and Beverage Services (FBS) is equipped with needed resources for success. The restructured TVL laboratory now serves as a training facility for our students as they prepare for the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) competency assessment to obtain their National Certificate II (NC II) in FBS.

In the school year 2024-2025, the school started doing Project IBLM all the way. Two TVL teachers gave two weeks of training to one hundred forty-six (146) students at Liliw Senior High School so they could take the free TESDA competency assessment. The goal is to get more SHS students, especially those in TVL, certified, which will make them more ready to get a job. The two specialized teachers taught about food service, focusing on the kind of work do in a restaurant. As a result, all 146 students (that's 100%) passed the FBS test and got their National Certificate II (NC II).

Getting a National Certificate II (NC II) from TESDA is a big deal for our TVL students, especially those in Food and Beverage Services. It shows they have skills and helps them get jobs and build their careers. Lots of countries accept TESDA's NC II, especially if they are competent with Philippine credentials. This makes it easier to find work overseas, like on cruise ships or in hotels. This shows that the TVL track is really helping students get ready for anything.

To ensure the IBLM project lasts, the school is focused on improving the restructured TVL laboratory. This will give a positive impact on education, skills development, and community well-being in the future. The school will create a strategy to gather funds for industry-based tools and machines that will support hands-on learning for TVL students. Upgrading vocational training equipment will help prepare students for real-world assessments. The school will also look for partnerships with local government units, non-governmental organizations, and private individuals to ensure the project's long-term success.